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**DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF 5G MOBILE TECHNOLOGY
IN THE WORLD AND IN AZERBAIJAN**

Abstract: *The research work is dedicated to studying the latest trends in 5G, the newest generation of mobile technology. For this purpose, the modern state in the field of fifth generation broadband internet services in the world was studied. Also, the current situation of mobile broadband internet in the Republic of Azerbaijan was analyzed, as well as the work done on the development of 5G services was studied. Comparative and statistical analysis, systematic approach, generalization methods were used in the research work. During the analysis, official documents, reports, and statistical indicators prepared by global organizations – International Telecommunication Union (ITU), GSMA Intelligence, as well as official data from the country's mobile operators and legislative acts were referred to.*

Keywords: *Digitalization, mobile network, technology, ICT, infrastructure, internet.*

INTRODUCTION

Digitalization of the economy is one of the key factors characterizing the development of countries in the modern era. The level of digitalization

of a country's economy is measured and assessed based on indicators related to information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure (Fətaliyeva, 2024). One of these indicators is broadband internet. Internet speeds of approximately 256 kbit/s and higher are considered broadband. This type of internet connection is suitable for handling large amounts of data quickly and reliably compared to traditional dial-up internet connections (Fətaliyeva, 2023).

A form of broadband internet is mobile broadband (2G, 3G, 4G, 5G), which is provided by mobile operators. The present study examines the current state of next-generation mobile broadband internet, specifically 5G, both globally and in Azerbaijan.

DISCUSSION

The current state of the mobile broadband market in Azerbaijan

Today, the coverage of mobile broadband in Azerbaijan is gradually expanding. The foundation of this type of service was first laid in 2009 – by the Azerfon company with the introduction of 3G technology. In 2012, the Azercell operator launched 4G technology.

Diagram 1

Mobile broadband internet subscribers in Azerbaijan (State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan [SSC], 2025b, p. 13)

The number of mobile broadband internet subscribers in the country is experiencing a dynamic increase. As can be seen from the data in Diagram 1, the number of this type of internet subscribers increased by 8.8% in 2021, 16.1% in 2022, 10.3% in 2023, and 5% in 2024 compared to a year earlier, reaching 9.2 million subscribers. In the same year, the number of

subscribers per 100 people was 90.4.

According to statistical indicators, during 2018-2024, the specific weight of the population living in the areas covered by the 3G network in the total number of the country's population has increased by 12%, from 72% to 84%.

Over the past few years, the number of 4G mobile internet users has grown more rapidly. As of 2020, 4G population coverage has surpassed 3G. In 2024, 95% of the country's population benefited from mobile services based on 4G (LTE and WiMAX) technology. (Diagram 2). With this result, Azerbaijan exceeded the world average (90.1%).

Diagram 2

Population coverage by 3G and 4G (LTE/WiMAX) mobile networks in Azerbaijan, % (SSC, 2025a, p. 12)

The increase in the number of Internet users who prefer the 4G network is due to the fact that mobile operators are increasing the number of stations working on LTE technology. For example, while the total number of 4G base stations of Azercell LLC was 3,124 in 2022, it increased slightly in 2023 to 3,431. Bakcell company has more than 8000 4G base stations. In 2021, the number of LTE base stations of the Nar operator was 2849 (*Nar, 2021, p. 23*).

Development features of 5G internet services in the world

Currently, the latest generation of mobile communication technology 5G is being implemented in most countries of the world. 5G has the potential to reduce latency and increase energy efficiency, and allows a large number of machines, objects, and devices to be connected to the network at the same time, providing high-quality and stable connectivity,

thereby boosting the development of the digital ecosystem (ITU, 2023, p. 20). For example, if the average download speed is 8 Mbps on 3G and 60-90 Mbps on 4G, this amounts to 150-200 Mbps on 5G. Also, the latency is 0.1 seconds in 3G and 0.05 seconds in 4G, while in 5G it is 0.001 seconds (Table 1).

Table 1
The speed of 5G mobile technology (Azercell, 2024)

Name of mobile phone generations	2G	3G	4G	5G
Average download speed	0.1 Mbps	8 Mbps	60-90 Mbps	150-200 Mbps
Latency	500ms (0.5 seconds)	100ms (0.1 seconds)	50ms (0.05 seconds)	1ms (0.001 seconds)

One of the main advantages of 5G is its potential to bridge the digital divide. Thus, this generation network can provide high-speed broadband Internet access for the population in areas where fixed networks were previously inaccessible (GSMA Intelligence, 2024, b, p.8).

The number of 5G connections, which were first launched in 2019, exceeded 1.5 billion worldwide by the end of 2023. Thus, it has been the fastest growing mobile technology to date compared to previous generation networks (GSMA Intelligence, 2024, b, p.6). By the end of 2025, the number of subscriptions worldwide is predicted to exceed 2.9 billion (Ericsson, 2025, p.1).

By the end of 2022, 34% of operators around the world had launched or tested private 5G networks. By the end of 2023, this figure had reached 64% (GSMA Intelligence, 2024, b, p.26). Globally, 5G is currently available in more than 100 countries. By the end of 2023, 261 operators in 101 countries had launched 5G mobile services (GSMA Intelligence, 2024, a, p.22). According to estimates, the global 5G infrastructure market size was \$9.1 billion in 2022 and \$16.7 billion in 2023 (Grand View Research, 2024).

The main barriers to the deployment of 5G are high infrastructure costs, device availability, and regulatory hurdles (ITU, 2023, p.20). The expansion of the coverage of the fifth generation mobile network requires

the installation of new base stations as well as the improvement of the existing infrastructure. A sufficient investment is required for this. From this point of view, it is important to have public-private cooperation. Along with private mobile companies in countries around the world, the government also pays special attention to this field. This highlights the importance of public-private cooperation.

In modern times, developed countries around the world are investing more in digital transformation, especially in technologies such as 5G and fiber-optic networks. For example, the Australian government has allocated \$21.2 million to accelerate the implementation of 5G in the country. The amount of funding directed by the Scottish government to the construction of centers related to 5G services across the country is equal to 5.2 million dollars. The government funding allocated to boost the digital revolution in the United Kingdom is \$38 million, while the French government's digital investment is \$8.4 billion (*GovTech Analytics, 2024, p.16*).

5G technology is expected to provide a greater boost to economic growth. According to research conducted by GSMA Intelligence, a global organization known for its research in the mobile industry, 5G is projected to contribute approximately \$900 billion to the global economy by 2030 (*GSMA Intelligence, 2024, b, p.8*).

Countries that have invested more in the development of 5G currently stand out with better results. The 5G Connectivity Index (5GI), compiled by GSMA Intelligence, studies and evaluates the state of 5G mobile networks in 39 countries. In 5G, which consists of 2 categories (5G infrastructure and 5G services), countries score between 0-100. The top countries in the 5G Connectivity Index 2023 were Kuwait (68 points), UAE (59 points), Norway (58 points), Finland (57 points), Qatar (57 points), Denmark (57 points), Hong Kong (57 points), South Korea (56 points), USA (54 points), Singapore (52 points) (*GSMA Intelligence, 2024, b, p.4*). As can be seen, the top performers were mainly oil-rich Arab countries, Northern European countries, countries belonging to the "Asian Tigers" group, and the United States.

According to the data of ITU, in 2023, the coverage of 5G mobile network by population in the world was 38.4% (*ITU, 2023, p.22*). According to another statistic from the organization, in 2024, the coverage of the 5G mobile network among the population was 51.2% (*ITU, 2025, p.29*).

According to the data of Table 2, South Korea is among the leading countries in the world in terms of 5G. So, when taken in proportion to the

country's population, there are 670 5G base stations for every 100,000 people. At present, a total of 346,460 5G base stations have been installed in this country.

China, which has the most base stations (4,251,000), has 301 5G base stations per 100,000 people due to its large population. However, this country ranks first in terms of the total number of 5G subscribers. The indicated indicator has exceeded 1 billion.

There are 152,000 5G base stations in Japan, with 122 5G base stations per 100,000 population. Japan is also the leader in the number of 5G subscribers per 100,000 people (Table 2).

Table 2
5G statistics in the world countries (European Commission, 2025, p. 24)

Countries	Number of base stations	Number of base stations per 100,000 people	Number of 5G subscribers	Number of 5G subscribers per 100,000 people
European Union	351,600	78	159,716,320	35,550
Australia	17,880	67	17,045,000	63,937
Brazil	22,800	11	36,527,346	17,300
China	4,251,000	301	1,031,825,433	73,142
India	464,990	32	160,285,747	11,146
Japan	151,985	122	149,916,953	120,399
South Korea	346,460	670	35,083,274	67,843
United Kingdom	23,100	34	57,285,304	83,812
United States	140,000	42	323,202,570	96,503

Work carried out in the field of 5G development in Azerbaijan

There are no statistical figures related to 5G in Azerbaijan yet. However, it should be noted that for the first time in the republic, Azercell mobile operator launched the 5G network as a pilot project in 2022 (*Azercell, 2023*). Following this, in 2023, Bakcell and Nar companies launched 5G technology in test mode (*Bakcell, 2024; Nar, 2024*). Full and widespread implementation of 5G in the republic has not yet occurred.

The issues related to broadband internet services are reflected in important state documents. For example, according to the Strategy for Socio-Economic Development for 2022-2026, one of the main goals in the coming years is to increase the coverage of broadband internet, including high-speed mobile broadband internet (5G) services, to 95% in the republic (*President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2022*). The Digital Development Concept also includes the expansion of broadband internet networks and the establishment of 5G networks as key targets (*President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2025*).

The 5G Strategy is intended to be developed with the aim of creating and implementing infrastructure for 5G, a new internet technology, for the development of the digital economy in our country. For this purpose, a relevant working group has already been established.

CONCLUSION

The results of the conducted comparative analyzes show that positive trends in the use of 5G mobile internet services have been observed over the past 5-6 years. Countries that have invested more in this area are distinguished by their higher achievements. The developed and several industrialized countries of the world are examples of this. In countries with advanced infrastructure for fifth-generation internet services, more users are able to benefit from high-speed broadband internet services, which results in an increase in the coverage of this latest generation of internet. In general, the expansion of 5G networks strengthens the innovation potential of countries and acts as one of the key factors of global competitiveness. As in most countries around the world, the use and coverage of the fifth generation mobile internet network will be expanded in Azerbaijan in the coming years.

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DÜNYADA VƏ AZƏRBAYCANDA 5G MOBİL TEKNOLOGİYASININ İNKİŞAF MEYLLƏRİ

Xülasə: Tədqiqat işi ən yeni nəsil mobil texnologiya olan 5G üzrə son tendensiyaların öyrənilməsinə həsr olunmuşdur. Bu məqsədlə dünyada beşinci nəsil genişzolaqlı internet xidmətləri sahəsində müasir vəziyyət tədqiq edilmişdir. Həmçinin Azərbaycan Respublikasında mobil genişzolaqlı internet üzrə hazırkı durum təhlil edilmiş, eləcə də ölkədə 5G xidmətlərinin inkişafı ilə bağlı görülən işlər araşdırılmışdır. Tədqiqat işində müqayisəli və statistik təhlil, sistemli yanaşma, ümumiləşdirmə metodlarından istifadə olunmuşdur. Təhlillər zamanı Azərbaycan Respublikasının Dövlət Statistika Komitəsinin, global təşkilatlardan Beynəlxalq Telekomunikasiya İttifaqı (BTİ), Avropa Komissiyası, GSMA Intelligence, Ericsson tərəfindən hazırlanan rəsmi sənəd və hesabatlarla, statistik göstəricilərə, həmçinin ölkənin mobil operatorlarının rəsmi məlumatlarına, qanunvericilik aktlarına istinad edilmişdir.

Açar sözlər: Rəqəmsallaşma, mobil şəbəkə, texnologiya, İKT, infrastruktur, internet.

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ТЕНДЕНЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ МОБИЛЬНОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ 5G В МИРЕ И В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ

Резюме: Исследование исследование посвящено изучению последних тенденций в области технологий мобильной связи нового поколения – 5G. В этой связи была проведена оценка современного состояния услуг широкополосного интернета пятого поколения в мире. Также был проанализирован текущий уровень развития мобильного широкополосного интернета в Азербайджанской Республике, а также изучена работа, проведённая в стране по развитию услуг 5G. В исследовании использовались методы сравнительного и статистического анализа, системного подхода и обобщения. В ходе анализа были использованы официальные документы, отчеты и статистические показатели Государственного Комитета Статистики Азербайджанской Республики, международных организаций – Международного Союза Электросвязи (МСЭ), Европейской Комиссии, GSMA Intelligence, Ericsson, а также официальные данные мобильных операторов страны и законодательные акты.

Ключевые слова: Цифровизация, мобильная сеть, технология, ИКТ, инфраструктура, интернет.

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